

DEVELOPING A PROTOTYPE CENTRE USING AGRICULTURAL SMART SENSORS TO PROMOTE AGRARIAN PRODUCTION WITH TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

This article presents the development of a model center using agricultural intelligent center technology. The goal of this research is: 1. To develop a wireless sensor network. 2. To be a source of learning on the use of sensor technology in agriculture. For local and nearby farmers Using the Sufficiency Economy Learning Center, according to King's Science. The Rajamangala University of Technology Suvarnabhumi is a research area. With the problems faced in farming today. It found that the world's climate change whether it's drought. Rains leave ranges and toxic airborne particulate matter caused by farming to match current problem conditions. The researchers then designed a two-part system: 1. Node Moisture Sensor that measures soil moisture and commands the opening – It also controls on-off with a manual switch. Wind speed and wind direction sensors, light intensity sensors, temperature, and humidity sensors, and Particulate Matters Sensor 1.0, 2.5, 10 with environmental reports within the growing area via Wi-F signals to (Sever) Raspberry Pi record real-time data. Every 30 seconds According to research, node moisture sensors can measure soil moisture and record results, and the station measures the environment within the growing area via a Wi-F signal to (Sever) Raspberry Pi. Rainfall values measured by local rainfall sensors measuring up to 35.3 mm are within the threshold of heavy rain. The maximum wind speed measured is 8.5 km/h, the maximum temperature of 35.8 degrees Celsius, and the maximum humidity of 99.9 percent, the light intensity is up to 58,002 Lux, and the Final Particles, with pm 1.0 up to 40.1 microns, PM 2.5 up to 51.3 microns and PM 10 up to 63.5 microns. Apply agriculture to 50 interested farmers after receiving knowledge transfer of smart sensor technology. The expansion has resulted in 3 farmers and will continue to expand in the future. Promote the use of agricultural technology. Intensifying communities and supporting global climate change.

Keywords: sensor, weather monitoring station, wireless sensor network, wireless sensor, weather station, smart sensor, smart farm, innovation, agriculture.

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1. Introduction

Modern technologies are being introduced in agriculture, including intelligent sensors for automatic retractable irrigation systems for vegetable cultivation [1]. Control and manage data

through smartphones and web applications [2]. With the evolving technology, sensors are divided into remotely controlled nodes with the Internet of Things (IoT) and real-time data monitoring via mobile phone systems (GSM/GPRS). Internet of Things (TCP/IP) services increasingly focused on the work of the modern agricultural sector [3, 4]. The Internet of Things (IoT) is becoming more common and increasingly popular in agribusiness to increase food production capacity for the expanding global population. With advancements in communication technology, agriculture sensors, and low production costs, parameters such as soil moisture, temperature, and soil acidity are measured. That wants to use a Low Power LoraWAN network that relies on photovoltaic energy. In addition, the 5G network technology is an up-and-coming innovation, offering innovative solutions for the modern agribusiness sector easily connected to intelligent sensors [5, 6].

Thailand is a developing country where the government has established the Thailand 4.0 policy, in which food, agriculture, and biotechnology are included in the country's development plan. Pushing Thailand to become a hub for premium agricultural and food production Agricultural production is the world's largest food source. Thailand has agricultural raw materials that have both quantity and quality potential. But climate change threatens to affect the farm sector. The effects of climate change include rising temperatures, diseases, and pests, water retention. Extreme climatic variability causes negative consequences for production processes. The ageing population is growing globally. As a result, agricultural and agricultural workers will likely decline. As a result of the slump and the proportion of farming populations steadily changing, Thailand's prospects will have an increasingly ageing population. Currently, in many countries of the whole world, including Thailand. It has focused on modern farming, also known as intelligent farms, with the global climate changing yearly. The problem of lack of workforce uneven yield. It affects productivity and prices in the market. Therefore, new technologies are essential to modern agriculture, where data can be monitored and operated through the Internet of Things (IoT), incorporating traditional farming practices [7–11].

In the past, the research team has conducted research. Vegetable irrigation and temperature control systems in greenhouses are grown with a network of zoning sensors in cultivation greenhouses. In **Fig. 1**, the system can control the temperature in the range of 37–39 °C, the relative humidity inside the greenhouse is 52.3–63.5 % and the soil moisture retention is 70 %.

Fig. 1. Vegetable irrigation and temperature control system in greenhouses because they are planted with a zoning sensor network

The panel then presented the development of a prototype centre for using agricultural smart sensors to promote agrarian production with technology. In the Center for Learning Sufficiency Economy, according to King's Science. Rajamangala University of Technology Suvarnabhumi.

In this research, the panel presented the development of a model centre for using agricultural smart sensors to promote agrarian production with technology and as a learning resource for the benefit of intelligent farm technology. In the local agricultural sector, electronic technology is connected to the Internet of Things in response to changing production patterns and the global climate. The system flowchart, which describes the operation of node moisture sensors and weather stations, along with reports of the environment within the growing area to (Sever) Raspberry Pi is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Block weather monitoring station diagram

2. Materials and methods

The panel [12] used soil moisture sensors to monitor soil moisture-through open-close irrigation water gates. Open and close the water gate via the Internet and monitor the data in real-time. The panel created a wireless sensor network consisting of 135 soil moisture sensors and 27 sensors to monitor the condition of orchard working areas in northeastern Italy. The deployment consists of 27 positions (vertical) connected by Multi-Hop WSN, each equipped with 5 soil moisture sensors at depths of 10, 20, 30, 50, and 80 cm and temperature sensors at depths of 20 cm. The panel [13] reviewed the literature on using sensor networks to monitor the environment within farms. Control and manage irrigation systems efficiently and help reduce the severity of global crises through Wi-Fi, Zig-Bee, and Bluetooth communication networks, which are the most widely used. The panel [14] monitored PM2.5 and CO₂ air quality in residential buildings under different ventilation modes in Xi'an:

1. To compare the pollution purification effects of two ventilation modes: natural ventilation and ventilator use.
2. To compare seasonal, monthly, and daily pollution concentration changes throughout the year to obtain residents' annual guidelines in using both ventilation modes and make appropriate recommendations.

3. To find the relationship between CO₂ and PM2.5 in two ventilation modes. This allows people to be aware of the lousy weather each month.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Node moisture sensor

Soil moisture monitoring by moisture sensor is formed into 3 nodes according to the area of planting vegetables. It measures soil moisture and sends it as an Analog signal to the Analog Pin port of ESP8266 and converts it into a Digital signal by serial transmission I²C [15] to make an open page – Electric Valve. In addition, the Raspberry Pi and its IoT can be operated in **Fig. 3** in case the Moisture Sensor or IoT failure can be used with a manual switch.

Fig. 3. The Block diagram of node moisture sensor

3.2. Weather Monitoring

In this section, the design of the wireless sensor network will be carried out. It consists of:

- 1) wind speed and wind direction sensors;
- 2) rainfall sensors;
- 3) light intensity sensor;
- 4) temperature and humidity sensor;

5) tiny particulate matter quality sensors 1.0,2.5 and 10 with an environmental report within the growing area to be stored in (Sever) Raspberry Pi.

3.2.1. Relative temperature and humidity sensors

Relative Temperature and Humidity Sensor (SHT11) Relative humidity (HR) is the ratio of the number of water vapours in the atmosphere. There are units of measurement in %, and the atmospheric temperature has units of measurement of °C in the range of -55 °C to 125 °C. The measured data are Analog to Digital converts connected to micro collectors (ESP8266) [16], shown in **Fig. 4**.

Fig. 4. The interfacing schematic for SHT11 to Microcontroller (ESP8266)

$$\text{Wind direction} = \frac{360 \times R_{A0}}{1023} \text{ degrees,} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{wind speed} = \left(\frac{217}{60} \right) \left(\frac{F_{osc}}{4 \times N} \right) \text{ km/h.} \quad (2)$$

3. 2. 2. Wind direction and sensors wind speed

The wind is the movement of weather conditions in a level way through a given point. The unit of measurement is km/h, the wind direction determines the wind strength clockwise between north and south, and the wind direction is expressed in degrees. The wind sensor consists of The wind-bearing propeller placed horizontally. The spindle is placed vertically, rotating cross-sectionally with a set of sharp axes. It Products a frequency of 0–60 Hz and wind speeds of 0–217 km/h to estimate the wind speed from the frequency measured by the wind speed sensor in 1 interval per cycle (N), with 1 break producing 4 pulses to convert to wind speed as equation (2) [16] shown in **Fig. 5**.

From **Fig. 5**, when the wind hits the propeller, it produces a strong wind. The air receiver blade then rotates, causing the spindle to intersect with the electromagnetic gas unit, creating an output pressure. For 360-degree rotation, the electromagnetic sensor reads the north-south axis of course as the Right Ascension (RA) as insignia 1 [16] and converts it to the wind direction, as shown in **Fig. 6**.

Fig. 5. The schematic wind speed sensors

Fig. 6. Wind direction

3. 2. 3. Radiation sensor

Solar light rays release energy from the sun to the earth’s surface. Therefore, the intensity of the sun’s rays or light intensity is a direct factor in the growth of biotics on Earth. In this design, the researchers selected the BH1750 sensor to measure the intensity of light that has converted the resistance, with semiconductors W, m^2 , shown in **Fig. 7** or photodiodes working when the bias is returned. When light hits the seam, P-N transforms the light signal into an electrical signal shown in **Fig. 8**. BH 1750 sensor can receive light in a plane of 180 degrees; the maximum measured light intensity is when the light is angled at an angle of 90 degrees.

Fig. 7. The interfacing schematic for BH1750 sensor to Microcontroller (ESP8266)

Fig. 8. Photo diodes

3. 2. 4. Rain sensor

Rain is a liquid formed in water caused by condensing water vapours in the atmosphere. Rainfall measurement is a measure of rainfall in a given place. Rainfall sensors consist of rainwater intake cones, rolled-switch beams, and rain beams. In **Fig. 9**, the water flows into the cone and hits the squirmer with a Reed switch as a normally open (NO) contact. When the read switch beam is struck, it changes the ordinarily close (NC) contact location into an electrical morphology [17]. It is sent to the microcontroller to count the number of times the splash – shown in **Fig. 10**.

Fig. 9. Shows a rain beam measuring unit

Fig. 10. Rainfall Detection Cycle

3. 2. 5. Particulate Matters sensor

Most farmers' farming practices in the area are done on open ground. In today's climate, air pollution is often found due to weeds and cane squash causing particulate matter problems that affect the health of the body, such as respiratory diseases, lung diseases, etc. PM 1.0 is a particulate matter of up to 1 micron in size. PM 2.5 is a particulate matter up to 2.5 microns in length, and PM 10 is a particulate matter up to 10 microns in size. In this study, the panel used a particle sensor PMS5003 series capable of measuring 0.3~1.0, 1.0~2.5, and 2.5~10. It is shown in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Block diagram of working particle sensor PMS5003

Fig. 11 shows a particle sensor PMS5003 working block by applying laser light to particles entering the air channels measuring 1 micron, 2.5 microns, and 10 microns [18] according to particle sizes in each area. When a particle enters the air channel, the laser light that passes through it falls on the particle, causing the light to squirm, causing the light passing through the receiving sector to have a reduced light intensity. After that, it converts the optical signal into an electrical signal and amplifies the signal to pass it on to the microcontroller for processing [19–22].

Node Moisture Sensor and Weather Monitoring station software are developed in the C language; communication between (Sever) Raspberry Pi and Node Moisture Sensor and Weather Monitoring station communicates via Fi-Wi signal with Module Fi-Wi ESP8266. In Fig. 12, the software works the system.

From Fig. 12, let's start by checking for accuracy. Potts input output from Raspberry Pie. After that, check the validity of the Sensor of ESP8266 (node1, node2, node3) and ESP32 (weather station, PM station). Done; check if the value from the sensor is received correctly. Read the

CONNECTION VALUE OF ADC signals, soil moisture sensors, and flow sensors emitted from pin D6 of all 3 nodes. ADC (Wind direction), dht11 readout form GPIO04, Wind Speed readout form GPIO14, Rainfall readout form GPIO32, bh1750 (light sensor) readout form I2C port record all sensor data, after which all values are forwarded to Raspberry Pie via Wi-Fi signal.

Fig. 12. System operating firmware

In Fig. 13, check the correctness of the operating system. After that, the operating system. Send the requirements to the sensor devices and wait for them to be returned from the Wi-Fi channel. Displays the values received through the operational system dashboard. In case, the requested weight or message device is not found via the functional system dashboard.

Fig. 13. Software System Operation

Development of a prototype centre for using agricultural smart sensors to promote agrarian production with technology. The researchers designed a node moisture sensor and weather station, along with a report on the environment within the growing area to be stored (Sever).

Fig. 14 shows a Node Moisture Sensor that measures soil moisture and sends it as an Analog signal to the Analog Pin port of ESP8266 and converts it into a digital signal by serial transmission. Every 10 seconds via Wi-Fi signal, the test results are shown in **Fig. 15**.

Fig. 14. Node moisture sensor

Fig. 15. Results of moisture sensor test

Fig. 16, *a* shows a weather station consisting of a wireless sensor network of 1. Wind speed and wind direction sensor 2. Rainfall sensor 3. Light intensity sensor 4. Temperature and humidity sensor and (*B*) Particulate Matters sensor 1.0, 2.5, 10 with an environmental report within the growing area via Wi-Fi signal to (Sever) Raspberry Pi to record real-time data. Every 30 seconds, the information presented is weekly. Experimental space, sufficiency economy learning centre, according to King’s Science. Rajamangala University of Technology Suvarnabhumi.

a

b

Fig. 16. Weather station consisting of a wireless sensor network:
a – weather stations; *b* – P.M. 2.5 Sensor and Raspberry Pi

Fig. 17, a shows rainfall values obtained from measurements from local rainfall sensors. The maximum rainfall value of 35.3 mm is within the threshold of heavy rain **Fig. 17, b** shows the wind speed obtained from wind direction and sensors wind speed, with a maximum speed measured at 8.5 km/h. **Fig. 17, c** shows the temperature and humidity values obtained from Relative temperature and humidity sensors. Air relative humidity is 57.1 cents, maximum humidity is 99.9 per cent, and minimum temperature is 25.9 degrees Celsius **Fig. 17, d** displays the Final Particles value, where pm 1.0 is up to 40.1 microns, PM 2.5 is up to 51.3 microns, and PM 10 is up to 63.5 microns. Based on the above results mentioned above, the research team transferred the knowledge of applying intelligent sensor technology in agriculture to 50 interested farmers and expanded the results in adopting intelligent sensor technology with 3 farmers.

Fig. 17. Weather measurement results: *a* – rainfall; *b* – wind speed; *c* – temperature; *d* – light; *e* – fine particulate matter

4. Conclusions

In this research, the centre developed a prototype centre for using agricultural smart sensors to promote agricultural production with technology. It creates 1 Node Moisture Sensor that measures soil moisture. Open – Turn off the electric valve with the sensor, operate via Fi-Wi on the smartphone, and control the on-off with a manual switch. Rainfall sensor, light intensity sensor, Temperature and Humidity Sensors, and Particulate Matters sensor 1.0, 2.5, and 10. These are smart sensor applications in the form of wireless sensor networks that communicate with each other. Fi-Wi collects data on (Sever) Raspberry *Pi* and analyses data for farming to promote agricultural production with technology and water management systems to achieve efficiency. Through our research, it is found that the developed systems can be used practically. In addition, the system can be used as a model to transfer knowledge on applying intelligent sensor technology to agriculture to 50 interested farmers. The expansion has resulted in 3 farmers and will continue to expand in the future. Promote the use of agricultural technology, intensifying communities and supporting global climate change. Based on research, it is found that the developed systems can be practical and serve as a model for applying sensor technology in the agricultural sector, Through our research,

it is found that the developed systems can be used practically and serve as a model for applying sensor technology in the agricultural sector. Create knowledge for farmers to use in farming as a source of learning for people in the community and nearby areas who are interested in and strengthen the community. The research concludes that the wireless sensor network (WSN) and Internet of Things (IoT) that helps drive the modern agricultural sector are, in addition to agriculture, an important tool for monitoring water quality for consumption.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest in relation to this research, whether financial, personal, authorship or otherwise, that could affect the research and its results presented in this paper.

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The study was performed without financial support.

Data availability

Data will be made available on reasonable request.

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